

EVALUATION OF SPLICE-TYPE CRACK ARRESTER UNDER MODE II TYPE LOADING FOR FOAM CORE SANDWICH PANEL

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1 Introduction

Composite materials such as carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) are commonly used in the primary structures of aircraft. However, the full potential capability of these materials cannot be realized because the present structural design concept is similar to that of metal structures, so-called black aluminium. Foam core sandwich structures are a suitable structural concept for integral structures that can realize the full potential capability of composite materials to reduce the structural weight and part count. Many researchers not only have conducted fundamental studies but also developed design procedures on sandwich structures [1-12]. We also conducted a study on the applicability of foam core sandwich panels for the nose structures of the commercial transport. The production trial test article of the nose structure is shown in Fig. 1. Through this production trial, 23% weight and 98% part count reduction were estimated using foam core sandwich panel structures. The foam core sandwich panel structure has a serious problem, that is, an interfacial crack between the surface skin and foam core, which is initiated from a damaged area, considerably degrades the static and fatigue strengths of the structure. The suppression of this interfacial crack is a key issue in enhancing the damage tolerant capability of foam core sandwich panels.

To avoid the degradation of strength due to an interfacial crack in a foam core sandwich panel, many studies have been conducted on interfacial crack propagation behavior and suppression methods [13-29]. Considering the application to aircraft structures, a simple crack suppression method with the minimum weight penalty is required. We have studied the innovative but simple crack suppression method of installing a material with higher stiffness on the crack propagation path [30-32]. This material with higher stiffness was given the name of a crack

arrester. The interfacial crack was suppressed by the decrease in energy release rate at the crack tip, which was caused by the redistribution of load between the foam core area near the crack tip and the leading edge of the crack arrester. A crack arrester with a simple configuration is shown in Fig. 2. This type of arrester comprises cylindrical CFRP material with 90° ply orientation in the foam core.

This method was naturally extended to a core-core splice, referred to as a splice-type crack arrester [33, 34]. A conceptual diagram of the splice-type crack arrester is shown in Fig. 3. The crack suppression effect of this method was analytically estimated and experimentally validated under mode I type loading [35, 36]. It is also important to evaluate the capability of the crack arresters under mode II loading from the viewpoint of structural integrity. This paper reports the analytical estimation and experimental validation of the splice-type crack arrester under mode II type loading.

2 Proposed splice-type crack arrester

A panel splice is an essential structural element in large integral structures such as the fuselages of commercial transports. The splice-type crack arrester provides a crack suppression function to a panel splice. A conventional panel splice consists of two tapered cores and a film adhesive between them. The splice-type crack arrester contains several CFRP plies between two cores instead of the film adhesive. A detailed diagram of the splice-type crack arrester is shown in Fig. 4. In this case, tapered core edges are replaced by CFRP filler to enhance the crack suppression effect [35, 36]. The results of numerical analysis and experimental evaluation under mode II type loading are described below.

3 Evaluation of the splice-type crack arrester

3.1 Numerical analysis

The crack suppression effect of the splice-type crack arrester was estimated by finite element (FE) analysis and the crack closure integral [37]. The ABAQUS Ver.6.4.1 FEM code was used. FE models of a foam core sandwich panels with and without the crack arrester were prepared. The FE model with the crack arrester simulated upper and lower CFRP surface skins, tapered foam cores and the crack arrester. The surface skin modeled Toho Tenax UT500/#135 solid laminate with ply orientations [(+45°, -45°) / (0°, 90°) / (0°, 90°) / (+45°, -45°)]. The core elements modeled Rohacell WF110 foam cores. The splice-type crack arrester simulated 4 CFRP fabric plies with ply orientations [(+45°, -45°) / (0°, 90°) / (0°, 90°) / (+45°, -45°)] installed between two tapered cores and two CFRP fillers replacing the tapered core edge. A schematic diagram of the FE model with the crack arrester is shown in Fig. 5. Mechanical properties of materials are shown in Table 1.

To evaluate the crack suppression effect, the total energy release rates at the crack tip were calculated and compared for the FE models with and without the crack arrester. A three-point bending load of 1000 N was applied to induce mode II type loading (see Fig. 6), which simulated the test load conditions. The total energy release rates at the crack tip for the FE models with and without the crack arrester were obtained and compared for crack tip locations of $L = 40$ mm, 20 mm, 5 mm, 0 mm, -5 mm, -30 mm and -50 mm under constant loading of 1,000 N. Here, L is defined as the distance from the crack tip to the leading edge of the crack arrester. The definitions of the energy release rates used in this paper are as follows [35].

- G_0 : energy release rate at the crack tip without the crack arrester.

This energy release rate was derived by FE analysis using the FE model without the crack arrester for a given load, P , and various crack lengths.

- G_A : energy release rate at the crack tip with the crack arrester.

This energy release rate was calculated using the FE model with the crack arrester under a given load, P , and various crack lengths. In this numerical analysis, a constant load P of 1,000 N was applied.

In the quantitative estimation of the crack suppression effect, the normalized energy release rate was used to estimate this effect. This parameter

is defined by $\frac{G_A}{G_0}$, where G_A and G_0 were calculated

for the same load and crack length. The subscripts A and 0 indicate data derived from the FE models with and without the crack arrester, respectively.

The relationship between the normalized energy release rate and crack tip location, L , is shown in Fig. 7. This figure indicates the energy release rate at the crack tip decreases as the crack tip approaches the leading edge of the arrester under a constant load. The shear stress distributions obtained using FE models with and without the crack arrester at the crack tip location of $L = 0$ mm are shown in Fig. 8. This figure indicates the decrease in the size of the highly stressed region near the crack tip. This decrease was caused by the redistribution of load between the foam core area near the crack tip and the crack arrester. This decrease in the size of the highly stressed region near the crack tip leads to the decrease of the energy release rate at the crack tip.

3.2 Experimental validation

The crack suppression effect of the splice-type crack arrester was experimentally evaluated using sandwich panel specimens with and without the splice-type crack arrester having dimensions of 620 mm (length) \times 50 mm (width) \times 39.2 mm (thickness) under mode II type loading. The specimen with the splice-type crack arrester consisted of surface skins, three tapered cores, which were spliced together with a butt splice joint, and two crack arresters. The materials, ply orientations and stacking sequence were the same as those described in the numerical analysis section. An overview of a specimen with the splice-type crack arrester is shown in Fig. 9. Prior to the fabrication of the specimens, the foam core material was heated to a temperature of 130°C for approximately 2 h in an oven to evaporate the water contained in the foam core. A Dupont-Toray Kapton film of 12.5 μ m thickness was used as a crack starter. The film was coated with Frecoat 700 to prevent adhesion. This film was installed between the surface skin and the foam core at a distance of 80 mm from the left edge of each specimen (see Fig. 4). The surface skins, foam cores, the crack arresters including CFRP fillers and the release film were fabricated in an autoclave with a one-stage curing process. A slanting angle of 30° was selected for the crack arrester to maintain a sufficient curing pressure

on the arrester prepreg during the autoclave curing process.

The test setup and test procedure followed the specifications in JIS K 7086 [38] because there is no standard test method for evaluating the fracture toughness of foam core sandwich panels. A crack propagation direction towards the obtuse angle side was selected as a conservative case to prevent the interfacial crack from being confined in the closed area between the arrester and surface skin, because an acute-angled condition might give inappropriate influence on the crack suppression effect of the crack arrester. A three-point bending load was applied to induce mode II type loading. In experiments, the initial crack length a_0 was 50 mm and the initial distance, L_0 from the end of the release film to the leading edge of the crack arrester was 40 mm. A precrack of approximately 5 mm in length was introduced by applying the mode I type loading. A servo-hydraulic fatigue-testing machine with 100 kN capacity (Instron 8501) were used for the fracture toughness test under mode II type loading. A test speed of 2.0 mm/min was considered to be suitable because of the relatively low fracture toughness of the core material compared with those of solid laminate specimens. Crack tip locations were measured with a traveling microscope at 50 x magnification. The test load and crosshead displacement were measured and recorded with a data logger. For some specimens, the crack tip locations could be visually inspected by applying water and orange paint on the specimen.

Two types of test specimen, with and without the crack arrester, were used. Fig. 10 depicts the relationship between critical loads, crack onset loads, and crosshead displacement. The crack tip locations denoted by parameters L were also indicated in this diagram. The critical load decreased as the interfacial crack propagated toward the loading point for the test specimen without the crack arrester. On the other hand, for the test specimen with the crack arrester, the critical load increased as the delamination crack tip approached the leading edge of the arrester. Then, the interfacial crack was arrested near the leading edge of the arrester. In the subsequent loading, the interlaminar shear failure in the laminate near the leading edge of the arrester occurred without any interfacial crack propagation. Just after the interlaminar shear failure, the shear failure of the core material occurred despite the lack of interfacial

crack growth. This fact indicates that the splice-type crack arrester completely stopped the interfacial crack near the leading edge of the arrester.

From the practical viewpoint, the detection of the arrested crack is a significant problem in applying the crack arrester method to actual structures. Regarding this matter, an innovative detection method using fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor has been developed [39, 40]. In this method, FBG sensors with a very small diameter of 150 μm are embedded on the both sides of the crack arrester with semicylindrical shape. If the interfacial crack approaches the one of the two FBG sensors, the reflection spectrum is changed by the higher stress in the crack arrester caused by the redistribution of load. On the other hand, the reflection spectrum of the other sensor does not change. By comparing the two spectra, the arrested crack can be detected. Application of this crack detection method to the splice-type crack arrester is expected.

From the design viewpoint, panel joints are an important structural element. To enhance their structural integrity, the authors have developed a simple method of retarding the crack initiation at joints [41]. In this method, CFRP filler is installed at the tapered core edge of a tapered-end-closure-type joint.

It is considered that the appropriate combination of these methods will lead to the realization of innovative structural concepts that will achieve considerable weight and part count reduction.

4. Summary

The interfacial crack suppression effect of the splice-type crack arrester was analytically estimated and experimentally validated under mode II type loading. Through the fabrication of a test specimen with the splice-type crack arrester, manufacturing data for sandwich panels with this type of crack arrester were obtained. This means that the practicability of this structural concept is enhanced.

From the design viewpoint, this type of crack arrester can provide a crack suppression effect for a core-core splice with a relatively low weight penalty. It is important to note that the splice-type crack arrester is not necessarily connect two surface skin panels as structural reinforcement, implying a small additional weight and a relatively simple manufacturing process can dramatically improve the structural integrity. Through the validation of the

splice-type crack arrester under mode I and mode II type loading, its applicability to large structural components in aircraft structures and the hulls structures of ships are expected.

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Fig. 1 Production trial test article of the nose structure.

P1	CFRP fabric	$V_f = 56\%$	$(+45^\circ, -45^\circ)$
P2	CFRP fabric	$V_f = 56\%$	$(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$
P3	CFRP fabric	$V_f = 46\%$	$(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$
P4	CFRP fabric	$V_f = 46\%$	$(+45^\circ, -45^\circ)$
P5	CFRP fabric	$V_f = 46\%$	$(+45^\circ, -45^\circ)$
P6	CFRP fabric	$V_f = 46\%$	$(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$
P7	CFRP fabric	$V_f = 46\%$	$(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$

Fig. 4 Detailed diagram of splice-type crack arrester with filler.

Fig. 2 Configuration of crack arrester with semicylindrical shape.

Fig. 3 Conceptual diagram of the splice-type crack arrester.

Fig. 5 FE model of the splice-type crack arrester.

Distance from leading edge of arrester : $L = 40, 20, 5, 0, -5, -30, -55$

Fig. 6 Mode II type loading conditions used in FE analysis.

Fig. 7 Relationship between energy release rate and crack tip location.

Fig. 9 Overview of the test specimen.

(a) Without arrester.

(b) With arrester.

Fig. 8 Comparison of shear stress distribution near the crack tip.

Fig. 10 Relation between load and crosshead displacement (mode II type loading test).

Table 1 Mechanical properties of materials used in fracture toughness test.

	Surface plate					Resin layer	Foam core
	CFRP (0,90) $V_f=46\%$	CFRP (+45,-45) $V_f=46\%$	CFRP (0,90) $V_f=56\%$	CFRP (+45,-45) $V_f=56\%$	CFRP UD 90 $V_f=56\%$	Neat Resin	Rohacell WF110
E_{XX} [GPa]	54.9	12.6	66.3	15.1	8.61	4.1	0.17
E_{YY} [GPa]	8.61	8.61	8.61	8.61	8.61		
E_{ZZ} [GPa]	54.9	12.6	66.3	15.1	127		
ν_{XY}	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.55	0.33	0.18
ν_{YZ}	0.052	0.023	0.043	0.019	0.022		
ν_{XZ}	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.022		
μ_{XY} [GPa]	3.23	3.23	3.23	3.23	2.78	1.54	0.071
μ_{YZ} [GPa]	3.23	3.23	3.23	3.23	4.23		
μ_{XZ} [GPa]	3.53	26.1	4.24	31.6	4.23		

